

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com)

Best Practice & Research Clinical Rheumatology

journal homepage: www.elsevierhealth.com/berh

Exploring the contribution of genetics on the clinical manifestations of systemic lupus erythematosus

Ruth D. Rodríguez^a, Marta E. Alarcón-Riquelme^{a,b,*}^a Center for Genomics and Oncological Research (GENyO). Pfizer/ University of Granada/ Andalusian Government, Spain^b Institute for Environmental Medicine, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Systemic lupus erythematosus
Genetics
Neuropsychiatric lupus
Lupus nephritis
Cutaneous lupus

ABSTRACT

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a complex autoimmune disease characterized by diverse clinical manifestations affecting multiple organs and systems. The understanding of genetic factors underlying the various manifestations of SLE has evolved considerably in recent years. This review provides an overview of the genetic implications in some of the most prevalent manifestations of SLE, including renal involvement, neuropsychiatric, cutaneous, constitutional, musculoskeletal, and cardiovascular manifestations. We discuss the current state of knowledge regarding the genetic basis of these manifestations, highlighting key genetic variants and pathways implicated in their pathogenesis. Additionally, we explore the clinical implications of genetic findings, including their potential role in risk stratification, prognosis, and personalized treatment approaches for patients with SLE. Through a comprehensive examination of the genetic landscape of SLE manifestations, this review aims to provide insights into the underlying mechanisms driving disease heterogeneity and inform future research directions in this field.

1. Introduction

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a complex autoimmune disease that arises due to the generation of autoantibodies that target self-molecules, forming and accumulating immune complexes that deposit in tissues, leading to inflammation and damage of the affected organs. Therefore, SLE is characterized by multi-organ involvement. SLE is more prevalent in women than in men, with a ratio ranging from 4:1 to 9:1 [1]. However, men typically have more severe manifestations of the disease. The clinical manifestations of the disease range from mild skin rashes to severe renal and neuropsychiatric involvement. SLE has varying frequencies of occurrence among populations and geographic regions. Studies have shown that individuals of African American, Hispanic, and Asian descent are more susceptible to developing SLE than Caucasians and the disease course is generally more severe [1].

Early diagnosis and prompt treatment are essential for effectively managing the symptoms of SLE and minimizing organ damage. In 2019, the EULAR/ACR (European League Against Rheumatism/American College of Rheumatology) recommendations for SLE management were updated to incorporate recent research findings [2,3]. These guidelines focus on the most commonly affected organs and tissues in SLE, which include the skin, joints, kidneys, lungs, heart, blood vessels, and nervous system. However, SLE can also affect other tissues, such as the eyes, gastrointestinal tract, and reproductive system. The severity and extent of organ involvement can vary widely among individuals with SLE.

Despite significant advances in unraveling the genetic aspects of SLE, the precise role of individual genetic variants in disease

* Corresponding author. Av de la Ilustración 114, PTS, 18016, Granada, Spain.

E-mail address: marta.alarcon@genyo.es (M.E. Alarcón-Riquelme).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.berh.2024.101971>

Received 6 June 2024; Received in revised form 1 July 2024; Accepted 2 July 2024

1521-6942/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

susceptibility and severity remains elusive. Our aim in this review is to provide a comprehensive overview of the current knowledge concerning the genetic basis underlying the most common manifestations of SLE.

2. Constitutional manifestations

The clinical manifestations of SLE are heterogeneous, with the most prevalent constitutional symptoms in new onset or recurring active SLE flares including fatigue, fever, arthralgia, and weight abnormalities.

Fatigue is a complex and debilitating symptom in SLE patients, affecting up to 90% [4]. The relationship between fatigue and disease activity in SLE has been under debate. However, it has been associated with several comorbid conditions, psychological factors, behavioral factors, physiological processes (such as oxygen/nutrient supply, metabolism), and specific organ involvement [5]. According to Felger et al. (2013), inflammation has been associated with decreased phenylalanine (Phe) to tyrosine (Tyr) conversion, which is the primary amino acid precursor of docosahexaenoic acid [6]. This decrease in enzyme activity may be due to the decreased phenylalanine-hydroxylase enzyme activity. IFN α has been linked to a decreased peripheral conversion of Phen to Tyr, which at the same time, is associated with a reduction in brain dopamine and fatigue. In light of this, disease activity likely affects fatigue in a complicated and indirect way as well as by impacting other important determinants like pain and psychological status.

Fever, not explained by infection, has been recently incorporated into the EULAR/ACR 2019 classification, reflecting its prevalence as a significant sign in 36–86% of patients [4]. While the reported prevalence of SLE-associated fever has decreased over time, potentially due to the widespread use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, it remains an intermittent disease feature. Fever episodes in SLE patients often manifest as low-grade and sporadic, necessitating careful exclusion of other potential causes before attributing them to SLE. Clinically, distinguishing between infectious and disease-related fever is crucial, with fever attributable to lupus correlating with lower complement C3 levels and heightened disease activity [7].

3. Renal involvement

Lupus nephritis (LN) is the most severe complication of SLE, resulting in increased morbidity and mortality. Whilst, the standardized mortality ratio for individuals with SLE lacking renal involvement is 4.8 [8]. For those with LN, this ratio jumps to 9.0, underscoring the critical impact of renal complications on the prognosis of SLE [8]. LN appears in around 50–60% of SLE patients at some point throughout the disease course [9]. Despite current treatments, only a tiny percentage of patients achieve LN remission. Furthermore, a significant proportion of individuals (5–30%) develop end-stage kidney disease (ESKD) within 10 years after LN diagnosis [8].

LN prevalence and clinical outcomes differ by ethnicity. Individuals of African American, African Caribbean, Hispanic, South Asian, and East Asian heritage have a greater frequency of LN than Caucasians [10,11]. Given the significant impact of LN on SLE, considerable efforts have been directed towards identifying genetic variants associated with its pathogenesis. To streamline research in this area, genes linked to LN have been categorized into four distinct classes: lymphocyte pathway genes, immunocomplex clearance pathway genes, innate immune signals genes, and kidney-specific genes.

4. Lymphocyte pathway genes

The major histocompatibility complex (MHC) region is a crucial genetic locus housing the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) genes. This genomic territory comprises approximately 200 genes, many pivotal in orchestrating immune responses.

The HLA region is renowned for its high degree of polymorphism with varying frequencies observed among different ancestral groups. Interestingly, a local ancestry study on an Amerindian-European mixed-ancestry group revealed that HLA risk alleles were of European origin, but protective alleles or haplotypes were Native American [12]. Additionally, there exist strong linkage disequilibrium (LD) associations between specific alleles of different HLA genes, resulting in the inheritance of haplotype blocks. Polymorphic variants within the HLA region were identified as early genetic risk factors for SLE and have since emerged as the primary genetic susceptibility determinant for this autoimmune disorder.

Haplotypes bearing the DRB1*1501/DQB1*0602 (DR2) and DRB1*0301/DQB1*0201 (DR3) sequences are consistently replicated in SLE in different ancestries [13–15] and also have been associated with LN [16,17]. In 2013, rs3135394 within the HLA-DR3 locus was identified as a susceptibility marker for LN, particularly in the context of proliferative nephritis. Subsequently, a comprehensive meta-analysis provided further insight into the relationship between polymorphisms in the HLA-DRB1 gene and SLE. The analysis revealed that while DR3 and DR15 were associated with an increased risk of LN, alleles such as HLA-DR4 and DR11 alleles may confer protective effects against the development of LN [18]. This research emphasizes the genetic complexity that underpins the development of LN and underscores the importance of considering specific HLA variation in risk disease assessment. Subsequently, a thorough sequencing examination of a large cohort of Han people encompassing the MHC region corroborated the associations [17].

Intracellular signaling pathways such as Janus kinase (JAK) and signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) are essential downstream regulators of cytokine activity. Upon activation, the JAK-STAT pathway facilitates the transmission of signals from cytokine receptors to the nucleus, where STAT proteins, including STAT4, modulate gene expression [19]. In particular, the activated STAT4 protein plays a pivotal role in enhancing the expression of genes crucial for the maturation of T-cells into specialized subsets, particularly Th1 cells. These specialized T-cells produce specific cytokines and orchestrate immune responses aimed at eliminating foreign pathogens within cells. T-cells in patients with SLE carrying the STAT4 risk allele rs7574865 has been linked to susceptibility to LN and poor renal outcomes in European SLE patients [20–22]. rs7574865 carriers exhibit heightened gene expression

of STAT4 in response to interleukin-12 (IL-12) and interferon-alpha (IFN α) promoting the autoimmune process [22,23]. Interestingly, in a phase I study, SLE patients carriers of STAT4 risk alleles had a more pronounced reduction in disease activity following tofacitinib, a JAK inhibitor, treatment [19].

The TNFSF4 gene encodes the protein TNF Super Family 4, also named OX40L or CD252. In the kidney, OX40L functions as a co-stimulatory factor to activate CD4⁺T cells. Activation of CD4⁺T cells leads to B cell activation, which in turn induces plasma cell accumulation and localized IgM deposition [24]. OX40L is expressed on antigen-presenting cells (APCs) such as monocytes, dendritic cells, and B cells. In a European SLE cohort, a significant association was found between LN and a genetic variant of TNFSF4 (rs2205960), yielding an odds ratio (OR) of 1.14 and a p-value of 0.0013 [25]. This association was corroborated in a Chinese population, involving TNFSF4 rs2205960 and rs10489265 variants [26], and more recently in the Latin American population [27]. Furthermore, individuals with LN, in comparison to SLE patients without LN, demonstrated markedly elevated serum levels of OX40L [28]. Additionally, in SLE patients, the expression level of OX40L on CD4⁺ T cells has been correlated with nephritis and disease activity [29].

B Lymphoid Tyrosine Kinase (BLK), a kinase involved in B-cell receptor signaling, is implicated in B-cell development and function. Variants of the gene BLK associated with SLE, such as rs2736340 [30–32]. Furthermore, rs2618479 and rs7812879 variants have recently been associated with renal disorder in Chinese SLE patients [33]. BLK interacts genetically with the gene BANK1, encoding a protein that upon B cell receptor activation, can promote Lyn-mediated phosphorylation of inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate receptors (IP3R). The SLE-associated variant of BANK1, rs10516487 in exon 2, causes a nonsynonymous substitution (R61H) and correlates with decreased splicing of exon 2 and a higher expression of the full length isoform containing a TIR domain [34], while a linked variant, rs17266594 is located within a splice branch point, promoting the differential expression of BANK1 isoforms. The TIR domain is involved in TLR signaling, and Georg et al., and Yu et al. have investigated the role of BANK1 in TLR7 and TLR9 signaling in B cells, *in vitro* and *in vivo* [35,36]. Interestingly, the BANK1–D2 isoform, which does not contain a TIR domain, displayed an inability to undergo K63-linked polyubiquitination *in vitro*. Since this type of ubiquitination is associated with increased TLR pathway activity and enhanced cell activation, their results suggest a mechanism by which the D2 isoform confers protection against SLE [36]. The rs10516487 BANK1 variant has been associated with SLE in both Europeans and African-Americans [37,38], and recently it has been associated with LN in Europeans [39]. Interestingly rs10516487 correlated similarly with SLE individuals independently of the ancestry while minor allele frequency was more heterogeneous among controls depending on the ancestry [39]. The genetic interactions between BANK1 and BLK observed in the north European and European datasets follow a recessive model for the BANK1 genotypes (rs10516483 CC or rs10516487 GG) and a dominant model for BLK (rs2736340 TT + TC) genotypes [30]. BANK1.

5. Clearance of immune complexes

A crucial mechanism underlying the pathophysiology of LN is the formation and deposition of immune complexes (ICs). By influencing IC clearance, Fc gamma receptor gene family (FCGR) and Integrin Subunit Alpha M (ITGAM) genes may act as mediators in the development of LN.

The ITGAM gene, encoding the α -chain, also called α M, of the CD11b integrin, has consistently shown associations with SLE [25, 40]. The dimeric integrin receptor CD11b/CD18, also known as α M β 2, Mac-1, and CR3, is strongly expressed in a range of leukocyte types, such as neutrophils, monocytes, and macrophages [41]. Despite ongoing research, the precise mechanism through which ITGAM SNPs contribute to the increased risk of LN and SLE remains elusive. Nevertheless, recent studies have begun shedding light on this complex phenomenon. Across diverse ancestral backgrounds, non-synonymous SNPs such as rs1143678 (P1146S), rs1143679 (R77H), and rs1143683 (A858V) have been associated with SLE and exhibit a higher prevalence among SLE patients with LN [40–43]. The three SNPs are distributed in different domains: the propeller domain (rs1143679), the calf-2 domain (rs1143683), and the cytoplasmic tail (rs1143678), suggesting their role in modulating CD11b-dependent signaling. Without altering surface expression, they seem to impair CD11b function, which includes integrin activation, ligand binding, cell adhesion, phagocytosis, and catch-bond formation. Allosteric activation of CD11b has been suggested as a viable innovative treatment approach for LN because of CD11's significant role in controlling systemic inflammation and autoimmunity [41]. Research including the pharmacological or genetic activation of CD11b demonstrates that allosteric activation of CD11b can reduce proteinuria, protect the kidney from damage, and control the aberrant TLR-dependent pro-inflammatory pathways in primary leukocytes and *in vivo*.

The FCGR gene family locus encodes Fc gamma receptors (Fc γ R), crucial for immune complex (IC) removal [44]. Among Fc γ R, there is one high-affinity receptor (Fc γ R1) and two low-affinity activating receptors (Fc γ R2A and Fc γ R3), along with an inhibitory receptor (Fc γ R2b). All these receptors are abundantly expressed in myeloid cells and show variable binding affinities to distinct IgG subclasses. Inadequate phagocytosis allows apoptotic cells to progress to secondary necrosis, releasing nuclear self-antigens and fostering increased IC formation in conjunction with SLE-associated anti-nuclear antibodies.

A non-synonymous SNP (rs1801274) in the FCGR2A gene causes a G-to-A allele change at position 131, converting arginine to histidine (R131H), resulting in different binding affinities for IgG2. IgG2-opsonized ICs are less likely to attach to cells homozygous for the arginine allele (131R/R) than to those homozygous for the histidine allele (131H/H) with an intermediate affinity to those with heterozygous genotype (131R/H) [45]. Several studies have linked the presence of the FCGR2A 131R allele to an increased risk of LN [46], indicating that the FCGR2A 131R allele causes defective clearance of IgG2-opsonized ICs, allowing for higher IC accumulation in the kidney and inflammation.

Similarly, rs396991 SNP in FCGR3A encodes the T > G allele mutation at nucleotide 559, changing phenylalanine to valine (F559V) [47]. This mutation causes an increase in Fc γ R3A affinity to bind IgG1, IgG3, and IgG4. Although the FCGR3A 158F allele showed a significant association with LN [48], in an extensive multiethnic lupus cohort, SLE patients homozygous for the FCGR3A

158V/V genotype exhibited a higher frequency of progression to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) compared to those with the 158F/V or 158F/F genotypes [49]. To elucidate this apparent contradiction, it is hypothesized that FCGR3A with low IgG binding capacity (158F/F) may be necessary to initiate LN, while FCGR3A with strong IgG binding (158V/V) may play a crucial role in exacerbating LN inflammation leading to ESRD [50].

In a recent study, the responsiveness to rituximab therapy was investigated in patients with autoimmune diseases who presented with FCGR3A F158V and FCGR2A R131H polymorphisms. The findings revealed a superior response in patients with the FCGR3A variant, whereas no significant differences were observed in those with the FCGR2A variant [44]. These results underscore the significance of personalized medicine in the treatment of patients with complex diseases.

6. Innate immune signals

IRF5 gene, situated on chromosome 7q32, encodes a transcription factor characterized by a DNA-binding domain and a polymorphic region, leading to the emergence of distinct isoform structures and functions. Functionally, IRF5 plays a pivotal role in the regulation of various cytokines and chemokines, including but not limited to interleukin-6 (IL-6), interleukin-12b (IL-12b), interleukin-17 (IL-17), interleukin-23 (IL-23), tumor necrosis factor (TNF), monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP1), chemokine ligand 5 (CCL5), and type 1 interferons.

Strong genetic association between IRF5, SLE, and LN has been reported [38,51–54]. Specifically, the IRF5 risk haplotype TCA, consisting of variants in rs2004640G > T, rs2070197T > C, and rs1095213C > A, has been consistently associated across ancestries [13,51–55]. Ethnicity plays a significant role in the genetic predisposition to SLE, as evidenced by meta-analytical findings. For instance, the rs2004640T allele, which creates a 5'-donor splice site leading to the transcription of an alternative exon 1B, is associated with SLE susceptibility in diverse ethnic groups including Asians, Europeans, and Latin Americans. Conversely, the rs10954213A allele demonstrates a notable association with SLE in European populations but not among Asian populations [56].

A recent investigation conducted within the Mayan population corroborated interesting findings regarding SLE and the expression of the IRF5 gene, previously reported in the Mexican population [53,57]. Despite the absence of disparities in genotypic frequencies between SLE patients and control subjects, SLE patients exhibited heightened IRF5 expression levels compared to controls possessing the same rs2004640G > T genotypes. Notably, control individuals with TT genotypes demonstrated elevated IRF5 expression levels compared to those with GG genotypes. However, this distinction was not observed among SLE patients, likely attributable to the influence of glucocorticoid therapy. Glucocorticoids, known for their DNA-binding capabilities, are speculated to impact gene expression dynamics, thereby potentially obscuring genotype-related differences in IRF5 expression within the SLE patient cohort [58].

The transcription factor NF- κ B orchestrates the expression of proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines, playing a pivotal role in immune responses. Encoded by the TNF- α -induced protein 3-interacting protein 1 (TNIP1) gene, the A20 binding inhibitor of NF- κ B (ABIN1) serves as a critical modulator of NF- κ B signaling by engaging with polyubiquitin chains on upstream regulators. Pathogenic mutations in TNIP1 can disrupt ABIN1 function, potentially augmenting NF- κ B activation and contributing to the pathogenesis of LN [59]. Genetic investigations have pinpointed polymorphisms within the promoter of the TNIP1 gene as predisposing factors for SLE and LN [60,61], with rs7708392 emerging as particularly noteworthy due to its identification across multiple ethnic groups [13,20,59,60,62]. Additionally, in murine models, Caster et al. demonstrated that knockin mice expressing ABIN1 [D485 N], an inactive form of ABIN1, develop glomerulonephritis similar to class III and IV LN in humans, characterized by enhanced activation of NF- κ B and MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinase) [62].

7. Kidney specific genes

Genome-wide association studies have identified risk genes for LN that are otherwise not associated with non-renal SLE [50]. APOL1 encodes for apolipoprotein L-1, a high-density lipoprotein (HDL) component. APOL1 is also highly expressed in a number of tissues, most notably the kidney. The transcription of APOL1 is upregulated by inflammatory mediators, particularly those induced via interferon-dependent pathways, which are often highly expressed in SLE blood cells and in the kidney infiltrating cells and endothelium [63].

The African ancestry (AA) population exhibits an estimated 70% excess risk of kidney manifestations [64], with APOL1 high-risk variants believed to substantially contribute to this heightened susceptibility although they do not fully explain it [65]. Furthermore, the presence of APOL1 high-risk genotypes is associated with both the prevalence and time to progression to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in patients with LN of AA [66], a correlation not observed in individuals of European ancestry (EA) [67].

The two APOL1 high-risk alleles, G1 and G2, in the APOL1 gene, have undergone positive selection in populations of AA due to their protective role against infection by Trypanosoma brucei rhodesiense (T.b.rhodesiense) [68], whereas these variants are conspicuously absent in individuals of EA [69].

The G1 allele includes two mutations in complete linkage disequilibrium in individuals of AA in the United States, rs73885319 and rs60919145, located near the C-terminal region [70]. On the other hand, the G2 allele is in the same functional protein domain but involves a six-base pair deletion, rs71785313. High-risk genotypes for APOL1 are characterized by homozygosity for either G1 or G2 (G1/G1, G2/G2) or compound heterozygosity (G1/G2). Approximately half of AA patients carry either the G1 or G2 allele, and around 12%–15% possess two alleles, constituting a high-risk genotype [68].

The HAS2 gene encodes the enzyme Hyaluronan synthase 2, which is essential for hyaluronan (HA) production, a crucial protein in basal membranes, but also an important factor in the evolution towards fibrosis in numerous organs. In the context of LN, renal fibrosis

appears as the primary pathogenic mechanism that leads to chronic kidney disease (CKD) and ESRD. Studies show that intra- and extraglomerular mesangial cells react to cytokines and growth factors such as IL-1 beta and PDGF, promoting HA synthesis by upregulating HAS2 [71].

Renal biopsy specimens from LN patients showed increased HA expression, notably in the mesangium and tubular parts of the kidney [72]. Furthermore, serum HA concentrations during the active phase of LN were significantly greater when compared to quiescent LN. The findings showed that anti-dsDNA antibodies stimulate IL-1 beta, resulting in enhanced HAS2 expression and HA synthesis by human mesangial cells [72]. In a European GWAS study, the HAS2 SNP rs7834765 was associated with LN with a 3.15-fold change [73]. HAS2 does not appear to be associated with an increased risk of developing SLE, but it does seem to be involved in the pathophysiology of LN.

8. Neurological involvement

Neuropsychiatric lupus erythematosus (NPSLE) is the term used to describe the neurological and psychiatric manifestations present in 80% of patients with SLE [74]. These symptoms impact the central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral nervous system (PNS) and can range from localized to widespread presentations, and vary in severity. Acute confusional state (ACS), anxiety, mood disorders, cognitive dysfunction (CD), headache, and psychosis are some of the most common symptoms. Notably, a meta-analysis involving 5057 patients suggests that a significant proportion, approximately 30–40%, of neuropsychological events observed in SLE patients can be directly attributed to the disease itself [75].

The heterogeneity observed in clinical presentations among patients with NPSLE has posed significant challenges in comprehensively elucidating its pathogenesis. However, akin to multiple sclerosis (MS), there is a growing consideration regarding the potential significance of blood-brain barrier (BBB) disruption in NPSLE. This hypothesis stems from the notion that in conditions of neuroinflammation, the barrier properties of the BBB are compromised, making immune cells and autoantibodies more accessible to the CNS, where they may provoke neuroinflammatory processes [76].

On a genetic level, several SNPs located on the TREX1 gene, including rs781221615, rs3135944, and rs11797, have been implicated in NPSLE [77]. TREX1, also known as DNase III, is an exonuclease with specificity for single-stranded DNA (ssDNA). Among these SNPs, rs11797 has gained particular interest because it separates people with NPSLE from those with SLE without CNS involvement [78].

Nevertheless, a 2011 study by Koga and colleagues found that Japanese SLE patients had a significantly higher cumulative number of risk alleles at eight established susceptibility SLE loci, HLA-DRB1, IRF5, STAT4, BLK, TNFAIP3, TNIP1, FCGR2B, and TNFSF13 compared to healthy controls [79]. Patients with over ten risk alleles had a higher likelihood of neurological involvement, suggesting that an increased number of risk alleles may contribute to the manifestation of more severe disease symptoms.

High disease activity, a history of significant NPSLE events, and the development of antiphospholipid autoantibodies (aPLs) are the main risk factors that have been consistently associated with NPSLE [80]. Furthermore, there is a correlation between cognitive impairment and cerebrovascular disease and non-SLE risk variables such as hypertension, advanced age, and conventional risk factors for cerebrovascular disease.

The vascular events caused by antiphospholipid (aPL) autoantibodies, such as lupus anticoagulant, anticardiolipin, and anti- β 2-glycoprotein-1 (β 2GPI) antibodies, are often linked to focal symptoms of NPSLE [81]. Serum anti- β 2-glycoprotein I (β 2GPI) antibodies, of either immunoglobulin (Ig)G or IgM isotype, showed an OR of 2.5 in differentiating between NPSLE and non-neuropsychiatric SLE in a SLE Italian cohort [82].

A meta-analysis [83] corroborated and elucidated a heightened association between serum anti-ribosomal P antibodies and NPSLE, particularly in cases involving diffuse manifestations such as psychosis. Notably, studies have demonstrated that anti-ribosomal P antibodies isolated from NPSLE patients induce neuronal death in the hippocampus and impair memory in murine models [84].

9. Cutaneous involvement

Approximately 70% of all SLE patients have some degree of cutaneous involvement [85]. Cutaneous lupus erythematosus (CLE) can appear separately, precede SLE development, or be a manifestation of the systemic disease [86]. Generally, specific cutaneous lesions of LE are categorized into three groups: acute (ACLE), subacute (SCLE), and discoid lupus erythematosus (DLE). ACLE is considered a symptom of SLE, but DLE and SCLE are clinically classed as CLE.

Acute cutaneous lupus erythematosus (ACLE) is usually linked to worsening systemic organ involvement and prolonged disease activity [87] and is classified into localized and generalized. Localized ACLE is characterized by sun-induced, non-scarring rashes over both cheeks and nasal bridge, commonly called malar rash or butterfly rash. Generalized ACLE is rarer and more widespread, characterized by symmetrically distributed, maculopapular erythematous, and sometimes edematous erythematous [87].

Some genetic variants seem to be associated with skin manifestations (e.g. FCGR2 rs1801274 associated with malar rash [25]) but only one monogenic causal variant in the TREX1 gene (also known as DNase 3) has been identified. TREX1 Asp18Asn dominant mutation has been associated with familial chilblain lupus, a rare chronic form of CLE. TREX1 is a key mammalian 3'-5'DNA exonuclease that cleaves single and double-stranded cytosolic DNA. Heterozygous or recessive loss-of-function mutations in the TREX1 gene cause defective exonuclease activity in Aicardi-Goutières syndrome (AGS), a rare juvenile neurological disease that clinically overlaps with SLE [88].

Ultraviolet (UV) light exposure is a well-known trigger for flares in individuals with SLE, particularly those with ACLE. This environmental factor can exacerbate the inflammatory response in the skin, leading to the onset or worsening of lesions. UV light

exposure induces aberrant apoptosis of keratinocytes, resulting in the generation of cellular debris that culminates in the production of proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IL-1 α , IL-1 β , TNF- α , IFNs, and CXCL10 [89]. A recent study found that lupus patients with TREX1 mutations had the highest photosensitivity to UVA exposure, followed by a substantial increase in UVB exposure and sensitivity to solar simulated irradiation (SSR) after 48 and 72 h [90]. When exposed to UV light, TREX1-deficient fibroblasts and keratinocytes produced higher amounts of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and were more susceptible to ROS-induced production of 8-oxo-guanine and global DNA damage. The 8-oxo-guanine DNA modification, which is frequently detected in lupus lesions, has been found to protect DNA from TREX1 degradation [89]. The mutated DNA is released into the cytosol during DNA replication and repair, it may activate the cGAS-STING pathway, leading to IFN-1 activation with ISG upregulation [89].

This causal relationship between the cGAS-STING pathway and lupus is further supported by a study identifying a heterozygous non-synonymous mutation (p.Gly166Glu) of STING in five members affected with chilblain lupus in a multigenerational family [91]. The mutation affects a highly conserved residue within STING's dimerization domain, causing multiple *de novo* intramolecular polar interactions that increase the inter-monomer contact surface area and improve dimer stability. Cells expressing the G166E mutation demonstrated a marked type I IFN activation in the absence of cGAMP, indicating that it acts as gain-of-function mutation. Interestingly, the treatment of two affected family members with tofacitinib, a JAK inhibitor, led to a marked suppression of the IFN signature.

10. Cardiovascular manifestations

While overall mortality caused by SLE complications has declined in recent years as new treatments have been developed, the risk of death from cardiovascular disease (CVD) in SLE patients have remained stable over time. SLE patients are 3–4 times more likely to suffer a CVD-related incident, including hypertension, vascular dysfunction, and myocardial infarction (MI) than people without SLE [92].

Several genetic risk factors have been identified as having a potential genetic impact on the risk of SLE-related CVD. Variants of the TNF Superfamily Member 13b (TNFSF13B) gene, the human low-affinity IgG receptor Fc γ RIIA (FCGR2A) gene, and the Methyl-entetrahydrofolate Reductase (MTHFR) gene have associated with subclinical atherosclerosis in SLE [93]. An Interleukin 19, (IL19) risk allele, rs17581834 (T), was associated with stroke/MI in SLE and RA patients but not in the general population. SLE patients with this risk allele had higher levels of circulating IL-10 and antiphospholipid antibodies [94]. Conversely, an SRP54-AS1 risk allele was exclusively associated with a transient ischemic attack/stroke in SLE patients but not in RA patients [94].

In patients with SLE, the ZPR1, APOA5, and GCKR genes analysis revealed a strong association between GCKR rs1260326 variant and carotid atherosclerosis. The GCKR gene encodes the glucokinase regulatory protein (GKRP), which stimulates glycogen deposition and *de novo* lipogenesis postprandially. The homozygous TT allele of GCKR rs1260326 destabilizes the glucokinase binding interface, leading to increased hepatic glucokinase activity, higher fasting serum triglyceride, and lower glucose concentrations [92].

A recent study revealed that SLE patients homozygous for the non-synonymous ITGAM rs1143679 mutation were associated with systemic calcifications, as evaluated by the T50 score. The T50 value is the time necessary to convert primary calciprotein particles to their secondary form in the patient's serum. Higher calcifications caused by ITGAM malfunction may contribute to the higher risk of cardiovascular disease found among SLE patients [31,40,95].

11. Musculoskeletal involvement

Inflammatory musculoskeletal (MSK) symptoms are common in SLE, being the first presenting symptom in around 50% of cases and affecting up to 95% of patients during the disease [96]. Despite its common occurrence, research on the genetic factors influencing joint involvement in SLE remains limited. Joint involvement is heterogeneous, ranging from arthralgia to erosive arthritis resembling RA. Historically, SLE-associated arthritis has been classified as non-erosive, in contrast to RA, and is consequently seen as a mild symptom that needs minimal care. However, the development of sensitive imaging methods has cast doubt on the idea of non-erosive arthritis in SLE. The usage of novel imaging techniques has shown that erosive damage can occur in up to 40% of SLE patients with joint involvement [97].

Despite the high prevalence of joint involvement in SLE, research on its pathogenic mechanisms remains limited. Most knowledge stems from studies on other inflammatory arthropathies, like rheumatoid arthritis (RA). Few studies have assessed the association between specific genetic variants and joint involvement in SLE. Notably, variants in genes such as ITGAM (rs1143679), C4, ACP5, mir146a (rs2910164), FCGR2A, FCGR3A, and STK17A have been associated with SLE-related arthritis [98]. A recent study reported elevated IL-17A and IL-6 levels in synovial fluid of patients with lupus arthritis, suggesting the involvement of the Th17 pathway, which has been implicated in various aspects of SLE disease pathogenesis [99].

Moreover, an association exists between arthritis and polymorphisms in the Vitamin D Receptor (VDR) gene. Vitamin D plays a pivotal role in immune modulation, including down-regulating Th1 immune responses, modulating dendritic cell differentiation, suppressing B cell proliferation, promoting regulatory T cell function, and preserving overall immune homeostasis [100]. Notably, SLE patients frequently exhibit decreased levels of Vitamin D, implicating its involvement in disease pathogenesis although the precise role is still under debate. However, while the study did not find an association between VDR polymorphisms and SLE susceptibility, it did highlight a significant association between the rs3890733 T/T genotype and joint involvement. Nonetheless, caution is warranted in interpreting this association since the observed genotype frequencies are not in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium.

12. Summary

As widely demonstrated, genetic variants play a critical role in SLE pathogenesis, contributing to the intricate interaction of immune dysregulation, environmental triggers, and tissue damage that defines the disease. In recent years, there has been substantial progress in understanding the genetic basis of SLE, with multiple studies finding particular genetic variants related to both illness susceptibility and disease presentation.

Although extensive data exist regarding genetic polymorphisms associated with renal involvement in SLE, investigations into other clinical facets of the disease are limited. Nevertheless, emerging research suggests that certain genetic variants may exert an influence on the development of SLE features beyond renal involvement. For instance, variants in genes such as *ITGAM* have been implicated in multiple disease presentations concurrently, suggesting shared underlying mechanisms.

Future development may suggest that the use of genetic data in clinical practice might completely change how SLE is managed. More accurate risk classification may be possible using risk algorithms that combine clinical and environmental variables with genetic risk scores. This would allow for more individualized approaches to monitoring and treatment. Overall, extending investigations into the genetic causes of SLE symptoms has the potential to revolutionize our knowledge of the disease and enhance patient outcomes by enabling tailored approaches to treatment.

Funding

This research was funded by the Swedish Research Council grant number 22-01000 and the Gustaf den Ve:80ars Fund (to M.E.A.R) and the Innovative Medicines Initiative Joint Undertaking (IMI-JU) 2 GA-831434 project 3 TR. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA. Disclaimer: content of this publication reflects only the authors' view and the IMI-JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

13. Practice points

- Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) presents a heterogeneous clinical spectrum involving multiple organs and tissues, with manifestations ranging from skin and joints to kidneys and the central nervous system.
- Genetic determinants, including polymorphisms in various immune-related genes, contribute significantly to the diverse clinical presentations and severity of SLE.
- Despite ongoing research, our understanding of the complex genetic architecture underlying SLE manifestations remains incomplete, highlighting the need for further investigation into the genetic factors driving disease heterogeneity and tailored treatment approaches.

14. Research agenda

- Extend large-scale genetic investigations, such as GWAS and whole-genome sequencing, to uncover specific genetic variants related to different SLE symptoms, expanding on previous research.
- Investigate the functional ramifications of previously reported genetic variants on immunological pathways.
- Further investigate gene-environment interactions that have been linked to SLE development, such as UV exposure, to better understand their function in generating specific SLE symptoms.
- Conduct longitudinal research to determine the role of known genetic variants in disease progression and the emergence of distinct SLE symptoms over time.
- Translate current genetic results into clinical practice by developing prediction models and biomarkers suited to specific SLE symptoms.
- Integrate genetic data with other clinical and laboratory factors to enhance diagnosis accuracy and prognosis for personalized medicine in SLE.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ruth D. Rodríguez: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marta E. Alarcón-Riquelme:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- [1] Sánchez E, Rasmussen A, Riba L, et al. Impact of genetic ancestry and sociodemographic status on the clinical expression of systemic lupus erythematosus in American Indian–European populations. *Arthritis Rheum* 2012;64(11):3687–94.

- [2] Aringer M, Costenbader KH, Daikh DI, et al. EULAR/ACR classification Criteria for systemic lupus erythematosus. *Arthritis Rheumatol* Hoboken NJ 2019;71(9):1400–12. 2019 Sep.
- [3] Fanouriakis A, Kostopoulou M, Alunno A, et al. 2019 update of the EULAR recommendations for the management of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2019 Jun 1;78(6):736–45.
- [4] Shaharir S, Gordon C. Chapter 37 - constitutional symptoms and fatigue in systemic lupus erythematosus [Internet]. In: Tsokos GC, editor. *Systemic lupus erythematosus*. Boston: Academic Press; 2016. p. 317–24 [cited 2024 Apr 5], <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128019177000371>.
- [5] Kawka L, Schlenker A, Mertz P, et al. Fatigue in systemic lupus erythematosus: an update on its impact, determinants and Therapeutic management. *J Clin Med* 2021 Sep 3;10(17):3996.
- [6] Felger JC, Li L, Marvar PJ, et al. Tyrosine metabolism during interferon-alpha Administration: association with fatigue and CSF dopamine concentrations. *Brain Behav Immun* 2013 Jul;31:153.
- [7] Guo F, Chen J, Xie Y, et al. Noninfectious causes of fever in 128 patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Iran J Public Health* 2019 Jan;48(1):62–8.
- [8] Mok CC, Teng YKO, Saxena R, et al. Treatment of lupus nephritis: consensus, evidence and perspectives. *Nat Rev Rheumatol* 2023 Apr;19(4):227–38.
- [9] Alimaani S, Meara A, Rovin BH. Update on lupus nephritis. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol* 2017 May;12(5):825.
- [10] Lewis MJ, Jawad AS. The effect of ethnicity and genetic ancestry on the epidemiology, clinical features and outcome of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Rheumatol Oxf Engl* 2017 Apr 1;56(suppl_1):i67–77.
- [11] Tanaka Y, O'Neill S, Li M, et al. Systemic lupus erythematosus: Targeted Literature review of the epidemiology, current treatment, and disease burden in the asia pacific region. *Arthritis Care Res* 2022;74(2):187–98.
- [12] Ziegler JT, Molineros J, Howard TD, et al. Genome-wide association study in an amerindian ancestry population reveals novel systemic lupus erythematosus risk loci and the role of European admixture. *Arthritis Rheumatol* Hoboken NJ 2016 Apr;68(4):932–43.
- [13] Alarcón-Riquelme ME, Ziegler JT, Molineros J, et al. GWAS in an Amerindian ancestry population reveals novel systemic lupus erythematosus risk loci and the role of European admixture. *Arthritis Rheumatol* Hoboken NJ 2016 Apr;68(4):932–43.
- [14] Kim K, Bang SY, Lee HS, et al. The HLA-DRβ1 amino acid positions 11–13–26 explain the majority of SLE–MHC associations. *Nat Commun* 2014 Dec 23;5(1):5902.
- [15] Sun C, Molineros JE, Looger LL, et al. High-density genotyping of immune-related loci identifies new SLE risk variants in individuals with Asian ancestry. *Nat Genet* 2016 Mar;48(3):323–30.
- [16] Louthrenoo W, Kasitanon N, Wichainun R, et al. The genetic contribution of HLA-DRB5*01:01 to systemic lupus erythematosus in Thailand. *Int J Immunogenet* 2013;40(2):126–30.
- [17] Xu R, Li Q, Liu R, et al. Association analysis of the MHC in lupus nephritis. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2017 Nov;28(11):3383.
- [18] Niu Z, Zhang P, Tong Y. Value of HLA-DR genotype in systemic lupus erythematosus and lupus nephritis: a meta-analysis. *Int J Rheum Dis* 2015 Jan;18(1):17–28.
- [19] Hasni SA, Gupta S, Davis M, et al. Phase 1 double-blind randomized safety trial of the Janus kinase inhibitor tofacitinib in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Commun* 2021 Jun 7;12(1):3391.
- [20] Bolin K, Sandling JK, Zickert A, et al. Association of STAT4 polymorphism with severe renal insufficiency in lupus nephritis. *PLoS One* 2013 Dec 27;8(12):e84450.
- [21] Reid S, Hagberg N, Sandling JK, et al. Interaction between the STAT4 rs11889341(T) risk allele and smoking confers increased risk of myocardial infarction and nephritis in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2021 Sep 1;80(9):1183–9.
- [22] Madera-Salcedo IK, Ramírez-Sánchez AL, Rodríguez-Rodríguez N, et al. Down-regulation-resistant STAT4 risk haplotype contributes to lupus nephritis through CD4+ T cell interferon-γ production. *Arthritis Rheumatol* 2022 Dec 27;75(6):961–72.
- [23] Hagberg N, Joelsson M, Leonard D, et al. The STAT4 SLE risk allele rs7574865[T] is associated with increased IL-12-induced IFN-γ production in T cells from patients with SLE. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2018 Jul 1;77(7):1070–7.
- [24] Sirin J, Suto E, Wuster A, et al. The ox40/ox40 ligand pathway promotes pathogenic Th cell responses, plasmablast accumulation, and lupus nephritis in NZB/W F1 mice. *J Immunol Author Choice*. 2017 Aug 15;199(4):1238–49.
- [25] Sanchez E, Nadig A, Richardson BC, et al. Phenotypic associations of genetic susceptibility loci in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2011 Oct;70(10):1752–7.
- [26] Jie Zhou X, Cheng F Juan, Qi Y yuan, et al. A replication study from Chinese supports association between lupus-risk allele in TNFSF4 and renal disorder. *BioMed Res Int* 2013;2013:597921.
- [27] Moreno-Eutimio MA, Martínez-Alemán CE, Aranda-Urbe IS, et al. TNFSF4 is a risk factor to systemic lupus erythematosus in a Latin American population. *Clin Rheumatol* 2021 Mar 1;40(3):929–39.
- [28] Farres MN, Al-Zifzaf DS, Aly AA, et al. OX40/OX40L in systemic lupus erythematosus: association with disease activity and lupus nephritis. *Ann Saudi Med* 2011;31(1):29–34.
- [29] Patschan S, Dolff S, Kribben A, et al. CD134 expression on CD4+ T cells is associated with nephritis and disease activity in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Clin Exp Immunol* 2006 Aug;145(2):235–42.
- [30] Castillejo-López C, Delgado-Vega AM, Wojcik J, et al. Genetic and physical interaction of the B-cell systemic lupus erythematosus-associated genes BANK1 and BLK. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2012 Jan 1;71(1):136–42.
- [31] Harley JB, Alarcón-Riquelme ME, Criswell LA, et al. Genome-wide association scan in women with systemic lupus erythematosus identifies susceptibility variants in ITGAM, PXX, KIAA1542 and other loci. *Nat Genet* 2008 Feb;40(2):204–10.
- [32] Jiang SH, Athanasopoulos V, Ellyard JI, et al. Functional rare and low frequency variants in BLK and BANK1 contribute to human lupus. *Nat Commun* 2019 May 17;10(1):2201.
- [33] Di D, Ye Q, Wu X, et al. Polymorphisms of BLK are associated with renal disorder in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Hum Genet* 2020 Aug;65(8):675–81.
- [34] Kozyrev SV, Abelson AK, Wojcik J, et al. Functional variants in the B-cell gene BANK1 are associated with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Genet* 2008 Feb;40(2):211–6.
- [35] Wu YY, Kumar R, Iida R, et al. BANK1 regulates IgG production in a lupus model by controlling TLR7-dependent STAT1 activation. *PLoS One* 2016 May 26;11(5):e0156302.
- [36] Georg I, Díaz-Barreiro A, Morell M, et al. BANK1 interacts with TRAF6 and MyD88 in innate immune signaling in B cells. *Cell Mol Immunol* 2020 Sep;17(9):954–65.
- [37] Martínez-Bueno M, Oparina N, Dozromov MG, et al. Trans-ethnic mapping of BANK1 identifies two independent SLE-risk linkage groups enriched for Co-transcriptional splicing marks. *Int J Mol Sci* 2018 Aug;19(8):2331.
- [38] Langefeld CD, Ainsworth HC, Graham DSC, et al. Transancestral mapping and genetic load in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Commun* 2017 Jul 17;8:16021.
- [39] Bolin K, Imgenberg-Kreuz J, Leonard D, et al. Variants in BANK1 are associated with lupus nephritis of European ancestry. *Gene Immun* 2021 Jul;22(3):194–202.
- [40] Halfon M, Zhang L, Ehrlichou D, et al. ITGAM rs1143679 variant in systemic lupus erythematosus is associated with increased serum calcification propensity. *Genes* 2023 May;14(5):1105.
- [41] Villanueva V, Li X, Jimenez V, et al. CD11b agonists offer a novel approach for treating lupus nephritis. *Transl Res* 2022 Jul 1;245:41–54.
- [42] Anaya JM, Kim-Howard X, Prahalad S, et al. Evaluation of genetic association between an ITGAM non-synonymous SNP (rs1143679) and multiple autoimmune diseases. *Autoimmun Rev* 2012 Feb;11(4):276–80.
- [43] Rhodes B, Firmrohr BG, Roberts AL, et al. The rs1143679 (R77H) lupus associated variant of ITGAM (CD11b) impairs complement receptor 3 mediated functions in human monocytes. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2012 Dec;71(12):2028–34.

- [44] Lee YH, Song GG. Association between functional FCGR3A F158V and FCGR2A R131H polymorphisms and responsiveness to rituximab in patients with autoimmune diseases: a meta-analysis. *Pharmacogenomics J* 2023 Nov;23(6):210–6.
- [45] Bredius RG, de Vries CE, Troelstra A, et al. Phagocytosis of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Haemophilus influenzae* type B opsonized with polyclonal human IgG1 and IgG4 antibodies. Functional hFc gamma RIIa polymorphism to IgG2. *J Immunol Baltim Md* 1950. 1993 Aug 1;151(3):1463–72.
- [46] Zuniga R, Markowitz GS, Arkachaisri T, et al. Identification of IgG subclasses and C-reactive protein in lupus nephritis: the relationship between the composition of immune deposits and FCgamma receptor type IIA alleles. *Arthritis Rheum* 2003 Feb;48(2):460–70.
- [47] Möckel T. B cell activating factor (BAFF): structure, functions, autoimmunity and clinical implications. In: *Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)*. *Autoimmun Rev*; 2021.
- [48] Karassa FB, Trikalinos TA, Ioannidis JPA, et al. The Fc gamma RIIIA-F158 allele is a risk factor for the development of lupus nephritis: a meta-analysis. *Kidney Int* 2003 Apr;63(4):1475–82.
- [49] Alarcón GS, McGwin G, Petri M, et al. Time to renal disease and end-stage renal disease in profile: a multiethnic lupus cohort. *PLoS Med* 2006 Oct;3(10):e396.
- [50] Iwamoto T, Niewold TB. Genetics of human lupus nephritis. *Clin Immunol* 2017 Dec 1;185:32–9.
- [51] Bentham J, Morris DL, Cunningham Graham DS, et al. Genetic association analyses implicate aberrant regulation of innate and adaptive immunity genes in the pathogenesis of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Genet* 2015 Dec;47(12):1457–64.
- [52] Graham RR, Kozyrev SV, Baechler EC, et al. A common haplotype of interferon regulatory factor 5 (IRF5) regulates splicing and expression and is associated with increased risk of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Genet* 2006 May;38(5):550–5.
- [53] Reddy MVPL, Velázquez-Cruz R, Baca V, et al. Genetic association of IRF5 with SLE in Mexicans: higher frequency of the risk haplotype and its homozygosity than Europeans. *Hum Genet* 2007 Jul 1;121(6):721–7.
- [54] Kottyan LC, Zoller EE, Bene J, et al. The IRF5-TNPO3 association with systemic lupus erythematosus has two components that other autoimmune disorders variably share. *Hum Mol Genet* 2015 Jan 15;24(2):582–96.
- [55] Hammad A, Mossad YM, Nasef N, et al. Interferon regulatory factor 5 gene polymorphism in Egyptian children with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus* 2017 Jul;26(8):871–80.
- [56] Hu W, Ren H. A meta-analysis of the association of IRF5 polymorphism with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Int J Immunogenet* 2011;38(5):411–7.
- [57] Nakazawa-Ueji YE, Valencia-Pacheco G, González-Herrera LJ, et al. Association of the polymorphisms rs179008 (TLR7), rs2004640 (IRF5), rs1800795 (IL-6) and rs2280788 (CCL5) with systemic lupus erythematosus in women of Mayan ethnicity from Yucatan. *Nucleos Nucleic Acids* 2024;0(0):1–17.
- [58] Ben-Zvi I, Kivity S, Langevitz P, et al. Hydroxychloroquine: from malaria to autoimmunity. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol* 2012 Apr 1;42(2):145–53.
- [59] Brady MP, Korte EA, Caster DJ, et al. TNIP1/ABIN1 and lupus nephritis: review. *Lupus Sci Med* 2020 Oct 1;7(1):e000437.
- [60] Adrianto I, Wang S, Wiley GB, et al. Association of two independent functional risk haplotypes in TNIP1 with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Arthritis Rheum* 2012 Nov;64(11):3695–705.
- [61] Azhdari S, Saghii M, Alani B, et al. Assessment of the association between TNIP1 polymorphism with clinical features and risk of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus* 2022 Jul 1;31(8):903–9.
- [62] Caster DJ, Korte EA, Nanda SK, et al. ABIN1 dysfunction as a genetic basis for lupus nephritis. *J Am Soc Nephrol JASN* 2013 Nov;24(11):1743–54.
- [63] Nichols B, Jog P, Lee JH, et al. Innate immunity pathways regulate the nephropathy gene Apolipoprotein L1. *Kidney Int* 2015 Feb;87(2):332–42.
- [64] Friedman DJ, Pollak MR. APOL1 nephropathy: from genetics to clinical applications. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol CJASN* 2021 Feb 8;16(2):294–303.
- [65] Chung CP, Karakoc G, Dickson A, et al. APOL1 and the risk of adverse renal outcomes in patients of African ancestry with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus* 2023 May 1;32(6):763–70.
- [66] Freedman BI, Langefeld CD, Andringa KK, et al. End-stage renal disease in African Americans with lupus nephritis is associated with APOL1. *Arthritis Rheumatol Hoboken NJ* 2014 Feb;66(2):390–6.
- [67] Yusuf AA, Govender MA, Brandenburg JT, et al. Kidney disease and APOL1. *Hum Mol Genet* 2021 Apr 26;30(R1):R129–37.
- [68] Genovese G, Friedman DJ, Ross MD, et al. Association of trypanolytic Apol1 variants with kidney disease in African Americans. *Science*. 2010 Aug 13;329(5993):841–5.
- [69] Thomson R, Genovese G, Canon C, et al. Evolution of the primate trypanolytic factor APOL1. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2014 May 20;111(20):E2130–9.
- [70] Alexander TA, Machiela MJ. LDpop: an interactive online tool to calculate and visualize geographic LD patterns. *BMC Bioinf* 2020 Jan 10;21(1):14.
- [71] Michael DR, Phillips AO, Krupa A, et al. The human hyaluronan synthase 2 (HAS2) gene and its natural antisense RNA exhibit coordinated expression in the renal proximal tubular epithelial cell. *J Biol Chem* 2011 Jun 3;286(22):19523–32.
- [72] Yung S, Tsang RCW, Leung JKH, et al. Increased mesangial cell hyaluronan expression in lupus nephritis is mediated by anti-DNA antibody-induced IL-1beta. *Kidney Int* 2006 Jan;69(2):272–80.
- [73] Chung SA, Brown EE, Williams AH, et al. Lupus nephritis susceptibility loci in women with systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Am Soc Nephrol JASN* 2014 Dec;25(12):2859–70.
- [74] Popescu A, Kao AH. Neuropsychiatric systemic lupus erythematosus. *Curr Neuropharmacol* 2011 Sep;9(3):449–57.
- [75] Unterman A, Nolte JES, Boaz M, et al. Neuropsychiatric syndromes in systemic lupus erythematosus: a meta-analysis. *Semin Arthritis Rheum* 2011 Aug 1;41(1):1–11.
- [76] Wen J, Stock AD, Chalmers SA, et al. The role of B cells and autoantibodies in neuropsychiatric lupus. *Autoimmun Rev* 2016 Sep;15(9):890–5.
- [77] Crow YJ, Chase DS, Lowenstein Schmidt J, et al. Characterization of human disease phenotypes associated with mutations in TREX1, RNASEH2A, RNASEH2B, RNASEH2C, SAMHD1, ADAR, and IFIH1. *Am J Med Genet* 2015;167(2):296–312.
- [78] Fredi M, Bianchi M, Andreoli L, et al. Typing TREX1 gene in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Reumatismo* 2015 Jun 30;67(1):1–7.
- [79] Koga M, Kawasaki A, Ito I, et al. Cumulative association of eight susceptibility genes with systemic lupus erythematosus in a Japanese female population. *J Hum Genet* 2011 Jul;56(7):503–7.
- [80] Jeltsch-David H, Muller S. Neuropsychiatric systemic lupus erythematosus: pathogenesis and biomarkers. *Nat Rev Neurol* 2014 Oct;10(10):579–96.
- [81] Devreese K. Standardization of antiphospholipid antibody assays. Where do we stand? *Lupus* 2012 Jun 1;21(7):718–21.
- [82] Govoni M, Bombardieri S, Bortoluzzi A, et al. Factors and comorbidities associated with first neuropsychiatric event in systemic lupus erythematosus: does a risk profile exist? A large multicentre retrospective cross-sectional study on 959 Italian patients. *Rheumatology* 2012 Jan 1;51(1):157–68.
- [83] Choi MY, FitzPatrick RD, Buhler K, et al. A review and meta-analysis of anti-ribosomal P autoantibodies in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Autoimmun Rev* 2020 Mar 1;19(3):102463.
- [84] Bravo-Zehnder M, Toledo EM, Segovia-Miranda F, et al. Anti-ribosomal P protein autoantibodies from patients with neuropsychiatric lupus impair memory in mice. *Arthritis Rheumatol* 2015;67(1):204–14.
- [85] Ribero S, Sciascia S, Borradori L, et al. The cutaneous spectrum of lupus erythematosus. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol* 2017 Dec 1;53(3):291–305.
- [86] Erazo-Martínez V, Tobón GJ, Cañas CA. Circulating and skin biopsy-present cytokines related to the pathogenesis of cutaneous lupus erythematosus. *Autoimmun Rev* 2023 Feb 1;22(2):103262.
- [87] Li Q, Wu H, Liao W, et al. A comprehensive review of immune-mediated dermatopathology in systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Autoimmun* 2018 Sep 1;93:1–15.
- [88] Demirkaya E, Sahin S, Romano M, et al. New horizons in the genetic etiology of systemic lupus erythematosus and lupus-like disease: monogenic lupus and beyond. *J Clin Med* 2020 Mar;9(3):712.
- [89] Gehrke N, Mertens C, Zillinger T, et al. Oxidative damage of DNA confers resistance to cytosolic nuclease TREX1 degradation and potentiates STING-dependent immune sensing. *Immunity* 2013 Sep 19;39(3):482–95.
- [90] Berndt N, Wolf C, Fischer K, et al. Photosensitivity and cGAS-dependent IFN-1 activation in patients with lupus and TREX1 deficiency. *J Invest Dermatol* 2022 Mar 1;142(3):633–640.e6.
- [91] König N, Fiehn C, Wolf C, et al. Familial chilblain lupus due to a gain-of-function mutation in STING. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2017 Feb 1;76(2):468–72.

- [92] Fanlo-Maresma M, Candás-Estébanez B, Esteve-Luque V, et al. Asymptomatic carotid atherosclerosis cardiovascular risk factors and common hypertriglyceridemia genetic variants in patients with systemic erythematosus lupus. *J Clin Med* 2021 Jan;10(10):2218.
- [93] Liu Y, Yu X, Zhang W, et al. Mechanistic insight into premature atherosclerosis and cardiovascular complications in systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Autoimmun* 2022 Oct 1;132:102863.
- [94] Leonard D, Svenungsson E, Dahlqvist J, et al. Novel gene variants associated with cardiovascular disease in systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis. *Ann Rheum Dis* 2018 Jul 1;77(7):1063–9.
- [95] Nath SK, Han S, Kim-Howard X, et al. A nonsynonymous functional variant in integrin- α M (encoded by ITGAM) is associated with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nat Genet* 2008 Feb;40(2):152–4.
- [96] Shumilova A, Vital EM. Musculoskeletal manifestations of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Best Pract Res Clin Rheumatol* 2023 Aug;22:101859.
- [97] Ceccarelli F, Natalucci F, Olivieri G, et al. Erosive arthritis in systemic lupus erythematosus: not only Rhupus. *Lupus* 2021 Nov 1;30(13):2029–41.
- [98] Ceccarelli F, Perricone C, Borgiani P, et al. Genetic factors in systemic lupus erythematosus: contribution to disease phenotype. *J Immunol Res* 2015 Dec 21; 2015:e745647.
- [99] Sippl N, Faustini F, Rönnelid J, et al. Arthritis in systemic lupus erythematosus is characterized by local IL-17A and IL-6 expression in synovial fluid. *Clin Exp Immunol* 2021 Jul;205(1):44–52.
- [100] Silva J de A, Fernandes KM, Pancotto JT, et al. Vitamin D receptor (VDR) gene polymorphisms and susceptibility to systemic lupus erythematosus clinical manifestations. *Lupus* 2013 Oct 1;22(11):1110–7.